

Received: 11 June 2021/ Accepted: 24 June 2021/ Published: 30 June 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5047615>

Effect of recycled composite on the thermo-rheological properties of asphalt binder

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This work was presented at the Fifth International Conference on Reuse and Recycling of Materials (ICRM-2020) held during 11-13, December 2020 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India, 686560

Introduction: Conventional asphalt binders have several limitations due to excessive overloading and varied climatic conditions. Significant improvement in performance properties of asphalt binder can be attained by incorporating various types of polymers, filler, composite, waste plastic, etc. (1-2). To lower the cost and acquire the required properties, recycled polymer composites is another alternative material to modify the asphalt binder. Research publications indicate that recycled polymers like PE, PP, PS, PVC etc. enhance the thermo-rheological property, rigidity, and rutting resistance of asphalt pavements significantly (1-3).

The current investigation is designed to prepare a modified asphalt binder with a recycled composite (4) consisting of SEBS and SEBS-g-MA toughened polypropylene, sisal fiber, and fly ash and examine the in-performance properties at upper service temperature. The main objective of this study is to utilize the recycled PP composites and attain the required performance of the modified binder.

Materials and Methods: Materials used to modify the asphalt binder are pristine polymer, followed by recycled composites (R_c). The recycled composites consist of fly ash and sisal fiber embedded in polypropylene. Thus, polypropylene was used as a pristine polymer to compare the physical properties among the modified binders. The modified binders were prepared by blending 5 wt% of polymers in the base binder (VG 10). Asphalt binder was liquefied at 180 °C, and the required amount of polymer was slowly added. The mixture was blended using a Silverson high shear followed by a low shear mixture at 180 °C. During low shear mixing, 0.14 wt% of sulphur was also added to make modified binder storage stable.

Testing methods: To measure the rheological behaviour of the binder, frequency sweep analysis was carried out by varying the frequency from 100 to 0.01 rad/s at 60 °C and 10% strain rate. The dynamic shear rheometer was operated using a 25 mm (dia.) parallel plate by maintaining the 1mm gap between the plates.

Results and discussion: The rheological property of modified binder consists of recycled composite (R_c) were measured and compared with pristine polypropylene and unmodified asphalt binder. Complex viscosity, phase angle, and rutting resistance as a function of angular frequency were analysed for the modified binders. The result illustrates that R_c modified binders exhibited higher viscosity than PP modified binders even after recycling. Among the R_c modified binder, the viscosity value is nearly same, which indicates the presence of sisal fiber and fly ash are insignificant. On the other hand sample with the highest dosage of fly ash exhibited the lowest phase angle value. Lowering the phase angle value may be due to the higher dosage of fly ash that stiffens the modified binder. Moreover, rutting resistance ($|G^*|/\sin\delta$) was also improved compared to PP modified and unmodified binders. Thus, it can be inferred that to improve the performance properties, recycled composite can be used as a modifier.

Conclusions: This study exhibits recycled composite (R_c) use during binder modification to explore the alternative method for utilization of waste composite. The findings state that the R_c modified binder showed enhanced viscosity and rutting resistance compared to unmodified and PP modified binder. In the future, the extension of this can be carried out for more comprehensive measurement.

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